

PERSPECTIVE

Priorities for research on neuromodulatory subcortical systems in Alzheimer's disease: Position paper from the NSS PIA of ISTAART

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[Correction added on February 1, 2023, after first online publication: The first name of the author Christoph Schneider was misspelled and has been corrected now.]

Abstract

The neuromodulatory subcortical system (NSS) nuclei are critical hubs for survival, hedonic tone, and homeostasis. Tau-associated NSS degeneration occurs early in Alzheimer's disease (AD) pathogenesis, long before the emergence of pathognomonic memory dysfunction and cortical lesions. Accumulating evidence supports the role of NSS dysfunction and degeneration in the behavioral and neuropsychiatric manifestations featured early in AD. Experimental studies even suggest that AD-associated NSS degeneration drives brain neuroinflammatory status and contributes to disease progression, including the exacerbation of cortical lesions. Given the important pathophysiologic and etiologic roles that involve the NSS in early AD stages, there is an urgent need to expand our understanding of the mechanisms underlying NSS vulnerability and more precisely detail the clinical progression of NSS changes in AD. Here, the NSS Professional Interest Area of the International Society to Advance Alzheimer's

Research and Treatment highlights knowledge gaps about NSS within AD and provides recommendations for priorities specific to clinical research, biomarker development, modeling, and intervention.

Highlights

- Neuromodulatory nuclei degenerate in early Alzheimer's disease pathological stages.
- Alzheimer's pathophysiology is exacerbated by neuromodulatory nuclei degeneration.
- Neuromodulatory nuclei degeneration drives neuropsychiatric symptoms in dementia.
- Biomarkers of neuromodulatory integrity would be value-creating for dementia care.
- Neuromodulatory nuclei present strategic prospects for disease-modifying therapies.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Despite making up fewer than 1% of neurons in the human brain,¹ the neuromodulatory subcortical system (NSS) nuclei serve as critical hubs for the processes underlying survival, hedonic tone, and homeostasis. Counter to ionotropic fast synaptic transmission, neuromodulation acts through slower, long-lasting signal transduction mechanisms to tune neuronal excitability. The NSS is a phylogenetically conserved network of nuclei located in the brainstem's reticular formation, diencephalon, and basal forebrain. Historically, the neuromodulatory nuclei were considered to encompass only those producing either serotonin (5-HT), dopamine (DA), norepinephrine (NE), or acetylcholine (ACh); however, more contemporary criteria consider whether nuclei produce and release molecules that act on neurons and glia by way of metabotropic receptors. These contemporary criteria expand the NSS to include nuclei that produce histamine, orexin, melanin-concentrating hormone, and dozens of other neuropeptides.^{2,3}

NSS nuclei are mostly made up of polygonal, unspecialized neurons with overlapping and symmetrically extending dendritic fields and broad, poorly myelinated axonal outputs enabling neurotransmitter release to extensive projection areas. The shared properties of NSS nuclei make them critical nodes for understanding, diagnosing, and treating neurodegenerative diseases. NSS nuclei are vulnerable to different neurodegenerative diseases and are believed to modulate several psychiatric illnesses. For decades, dysfunction and degeneration (including tau accumulation, decreased transmitter production, synapse loss, and neuron loss) of the NSS have been well documented in Alzheimer's disease (AD), with particular focus on the cholinergic basal forebrain (CBF).^{4–12} In fact, the prevailing treatment for AD targets cholinergic system dysfunction.¹³ More recent work has provided a full appreciation of the early involvement, severity, and clinical consequences of NSS dysfunction and degeneration in AD, with bodies of literature growing around the

locus coeruleus (LC), dorsal raphe nucleus (DRN), hypothalamic nuclei, and others.

In the early 2000s, findings describing the extensive degeneration of lower brainstem nuclei preceding substantia nigra (SN) involvement in Lewy body disease (LBD)¹⁴ challenged early beliefs that Parkinsonism was the earliest manifestation of LBD. Later studies confirmed the association between alpha-synuclein-driven degeneration of caudal brainstem nuclei and early non-motor features of synucleinopathies, such as rapid eye movement (REM) sleep disorder and hyperalgesia.¹⁵

These findings in LBD inspired interest in re-examining the chronology of NSS involvement in AD. Independent studies showed that NSS degeneration, including intraneuronal tau aggregation, diminished neuron viability, and cell and synaptic loss, occurs early in AD pathogenesis.¹⁶ At least 15 NSS components, including noradrenergic, serotonergic, cholinergic, and orexinergic nuclei, show abnormal tau neuronal inclusions at Braak stage 0 (i.e., preceding tau pathological lesions in the entorhinal cortex).¹⁷ Like in LBD, NSS dysfunction and degeneration manifest as non-pathognomonic symptoms in AD. In the case of AD, changes in sleep, vigilance, affect, and appetite precede memory decline and relate to underlying NSS degeneration.^{18,19} The relevance of early NSS dysfunction in AD goes beyond just clinical manifestations. Experimental studies show systematic effects of AD-related NSS degeneration resulting in dysregulated neuroinflammation, cortical tau seeding, and exacerbated cortical plaque accumulation.^{20–27} The bi-directional relationships between NSS vulnerability and cortical dysfunction and degeneration are underexplored but have important implications for clinical practice and pathogenesis.

The molecular basis of selective vulnerability of NSS nuclei in AD is poorly understood but likely linked to the shared properties of these nuclei. NSS neurons regulate cognition and behavior via long, unmyelinated projections from neurons with relatively high metabolic activity. Additionally, these nuclei require high gene and protein turnover

FIGURE 1 The neuromodulatory subcortical system (NSS) professional interest area recommends investment in research on pathways to selective vulnerability in NSS and how dysfunction and degeneration of NSS contribute to pathogenesis and clinical consequences. Myriad disciplines are positioned to generate knowledge within any of these research themes

rates to maintain the cytoskeletal integrity necessary to regulate axonal trafficking/transmission and multi-modal dendritic inputs.^{28–32} Finally, the NSS is strategically positioned close to circumventricular organs of the blood–brain barrier, making them uniquely vulnerable to neurovascular contributors to neurodegeneration.^{33–35}

The NSS professional interest area (PIA) of the International Society to Advance Alzheimer's Research and Treatment (ISTAART) seeks to congregate a multidisciplinary community of researchers and clinicians with expertise in these highly vulnerable and behaviorally impactful structures. Addressing AD-driven NSS dysfunction and degeneration is a promising strategy to identify, monitor, and modify AD progression from what are currently considered presymptomatic stages. The need for early detection and intervention in AD is widely accepted, but, despite their early involvement, NSS changes in AD remain underrecognized, understudied, and undertreated. The NSS PIA cross-disciplinary efforts seek to improve early detection and intervention in AD by (1) elucidating pathways to selective vulnerability of the NSS in AD and (2) characterizing outcomes and implications of NSS dysfunction and degeneration (Figure 1). In this position paper, professional

RESEARCH IN CONTEXT

- 1. Systematic review:** The authors reviewed literature using PubMed and preprint servers. While the majority of the literature on neuromodulatory subcortical systems in Alzheimer's disease has focused on the locus coeruleus, there is emerging evidence for similar manifestations in other neuromodulatory subcortical structures. We have emphasized this recent literature to draw attention to the relevance of the whole neuromodulatory subcortical system. Such relevant citations are appropriately cited.
- 2. Interpretation:** This position paper provides context and recommendations for future research on and funding strategies for neuromodulatory subcortical systems in Alzheimer's disease.
- 3. Future directions:** The Neuromodulatory Subcortical Systems (NSS) Professional Interest Area of ISTAART recommends increased funding and focus for research on pathways to selective vulnerability of NSS, biomarkers of NSS integrity, clinical manifestations of NSS degeneration, and symptomatic and disease-modifying treatments for Alzheimer's-type dementia targeting the NSS.

community members specializing in NSS contribute their insights on knowledge gaps within AD and provide recommendations for priorities specific to clinical research, biomarker development, modeling, and interventions focusing on AD-related NSS degeneration. For this position paper, AD tau-mediated NSS degeneration is considered part of AD neuropathological stages even in the absence of amyloid beta ($A\beta$) cortical plaques.^{36,37}

2 | CLINICAL RESEARCH

2.1 | Cohort design

By the time individuals with AD pathology manifest episodic memory loss in typical amnesic AD, NSS atrophy and dysregulation have already reached moderate stages.¹⁷ Thus, cohorts from population-based aging studies are more suitable than clinical dementia cohorts to inform on NSS selective vulnerability because they will capture transition phases when dysfunction and degeneration of NSS nuclei begin. Enriching these cohorts with participants presenting with subjective memory decline³⁸ and mild behavioral impairment may be required to reach sufficient power to detect changes in NSS. Investigating AD-mediated NSS degeneration requires longitudinal observations and better tools to track granular neuropsychiatric symptoms, subtle cognitive changes, and responses to psychotropic medications. Such cohorts should incorporate existing “amyloid/tau/neurodegeneration (ATN)”-type biomarkers³⁹ and prioritize enrollment in autopsy studies. Inclusion criteria should prioritize phenotypes such as adult incidence

of unexplained affective symptoms or changes in sleep, vigilance, and appetite.

2.2 | Biomarkers

Neuroimaging has the potential to inform novel perspectives on the dynamic NSS changes in aging and AD and how they might underscore cognitive-behavioral aging trajectories. Recent years have featured a vast improvement in neuroimaging tools to detect the neuromelanin-containing LC and SN in clinical settings in clinically feasible acquisition times.^{40–42} Expanding the neuroimager's toolbox to include the detection of other NSS nuclei is a needed but challenging goal because of the size and location of these nuclei. Emerging acquisition sequences and analytical pipelines using deep learning to identify several hypothalamic subregions⁴³ and the basal forebrain^{44,45} based on standard structural neuroimaging are catalyzing this front, but constraints to spatial resolution jeopardize sensitive evaluation of NSS. For example, even the novel pipelines to segment the hypothalamus can only resolve groupings of nuclei as hypothalamic subunits, rather than single subnuclei (e.g., the inferior tubular subunit which includes the infundibular nucleus, ventromedial nucleus, supraoptic nucleus, lateral tubular nucleus, and tuberomammillary nucleus).⁴³ Expanding adoption of 7T ultra-high-field magnetic resonance imaging and approaches to address noise, such as multi-echo functional sequences^{46,47} and multiband imaging,^{48,49} may offer solutions. Positron emission tomography ligands specific to NSS and blood oxygenation level-dependent imaging⁵⁰ may provide further information about NSS function and integrity.^{51,52} Novel neuroimaging methods must leverage effective data sharing and granular *post mortem* validation to improve standardization, reproducibility, and understanding of biological correlations.

Evolving analytical chemistry techniques make evaluating biofluids' neuromodulator and associated metabolite levels more feasible and affordable. Still, it has been challenging to interpret plasma and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) levels of neuromodulators and their metabolites. CSF neuromodulator levels may have an inverted U-shape in AD because of compensatory overexpression or increased release during the early stages of AD-related NSS changes.^{18,53} Moreover, several neuromodulators are produced in the peripheral nervous system. For example, NE detected in saliva and plasma likely reflects peripheral activity rather than LC function. Thus, target detection in CSF likely represents NSS functional integrity best because blood-brain barrier dynamics and peripheral activity influence it less. However, it is not without influence from these variables or analytical differences.

Due to roles in upregulating sympathetic and downregulating parasympathetic activity, the integrity of NSS structures like the LC may also covary with physiological indices such as heart rate variability,^{54,55} pupil diameter changes,^{56–61} skin conductance, salivary amylase, saccadic and smooth pursuit eye movements, and critical flicker fusion threshold. All of these indices have been explored as functional readouts of NSS changes. Pupillometry has garnered much attention as a tool to evaluate LC integrity and may aid AD clinical stratification,^{62–64} but its utility remains unclear. Numerous NSS

nuclei, including the cholinergic system, modulate pupil dilation, making it more likely a marker of NSS integrity as a whole than a specific LC marker. Scalp electrophysiologic recordings may also serve as a useful biomarker in AD^{65,66} and, as an index of cortical arousal, should be explored as a measure of NSS functional integrity. Systematic neuropathological studies addressing the human NSS along AD progression are critical to inform biomarker development and its integration with clinical studies or diagnostic paradigms.

2.3 | Clinical assessment

An extensive functional neuroanatomic literature and mounting research specific to AD over the past decade have highlighted the tight associations between AD-related NSS dysfunction and neuropsychological manifestations of AD. Individuals with AD pathology can experience a constellation of behavioral and psychiatric symptoms such as apathy, depression, anxiety, irritability, agitation and aggression, delusions, eating disorder, aberrant motor behavior, wandering and sundowning, hallucinations, sleep-wake cycle disorder, disinhibition, elation, and mania.^{62,63} Such symptoms negatively affect patients' quality of life and caregiver burden, leading to higher institutionalization rates.^{64–66}

Affective symptoms are the most prevalent neuropsychiatric manifestation among people with AD-type dementia.⁶⁷ Dysregulation of subcortical regions such as the LC and hypothalamic nuclei are conventionally associated with anxiety.^{68,69} While depression has historically been more closely related to the deterioration of the frontal-subcortical-limbic circuit, early AD-related degeneration of the serotonergic DRN has been neglected in clinical and biomarker research and may contribute to depressive mood. Agitation and anxiety are related to AD progression due to impaired emotional regulation networks,⁷⁰ and certain neurochemical disturbances, including potential compensatory overactivity of the noradrenergic system.⁷¹

Diurnal and nocturnal polysomnographic studies in AD patients report sleep fragmentation, diurnal sleepiness with increased napping, and a prominent decrease in slow-wave⁷² and an average or modest decline in total sleep and REM sleep time.⁷³ A combination of early tau-associated dysregulation and degeneration of the noradrenergic, orexinergic, histaminergic, and basal forebrain cholinergic systems, all critical nodes in the ascending arousal network that organizes the sleep-wake cycle, contributes to sleep disturbances in AD.^{19,74–82} Sleep disturbances precede memory decline in a significant portion of AD patients. Even during the early stages, these disturbances may also contribute to diminished sleep-dependent brain maintenance, which, in turn, exacerbates the propagation of AD protein hallmarks creating a positive feedback loop.^{76,83} Consequently, sleep dysfunction has emerged as a promising modifiable risk factor for delaying or slowing initial AD-related processes before the onset of dementia.

Beyond psychiatric and behavioral manifestations, the NSS critically contributes to higher order cognitive functions such as attention and memory.^{84–87} Degeneration of NSS have thus been proposed as significant determinants of cognitive decline.^{53,88–90} In line with this,

correlative evidence links dopaminergic⁹¹⁻⁹³ and noradrenergic⁹⁴⁻⁹⁶ neuromodulation to cognition.

Currently, psychometric assessment tools for individuals with AD, such as the Neuropsychiatric Inventory (NPI),⁹⁷ rely on retrospective subjective ratings by proxy, which are vulnerable to recall bias in quasi-experimental clinical settings. Digital instruments can assess affect, sleep, vigilance, agitation, social behavior, and psychiatric manifestations via objective and immediate measures in ecologically valid (e.g., in-home) settings.^{98,99} Furthermore, more sensitive, ecologically valid neuropsychiatric instruments may offer advantages for monitoring the success of disease-modifying therapeutics compared to evaluating cognitive changes alone. Validation of non-intrusive digital sensing systems to capture early cognitive, behavioral, and physiological impairments in preclinical and prodromal AD is ongoing in international multicohort studies.

Observational studies in aging populations should carefully track the numerous psychiatric and behavioral changes associated with dementia in a detailed manner. Cross-disciplinary efforts with groups such as the ISTAART Neuropsychiatric Symptoms, Sleep, and Technology and Dementia PIAs may help to mobilize these efforts. Furthermore, the accumulating evidence of clinical consequences associated with early NSS degeneration in AD pathogenesis begs the question if, despite the lack of specificity for AD, syndromic definitions should be expanded to incorporate non-cognitive symptoms as early manifestations of AD-type neuropathologic lesions.

2.4 | Neuropathology

Despite the exponential gain of knowledge about AD-related NSS pathology in the past years, many gaps remain. Although more than a dozen NSS nuclei develop AD-tau inclusions preceding changes in the transentorhinal cortex (i.e., before Braak stage I) and others develop AD-type inclusions at very early Braak stages,^{16,17,100} systematic neuropathological investigations have mainly focused on the LC, DRN, and CBF.^{75,101-104} Moreover, the relationship and timing between the appearance of AD-like neuropathologic inclusions (e.g., hyperphosphorylated tau) and the frank degeneration of NSS nuclei (e.g., loss of axons or cell bodies) have rarely been rigorously characterized.

Existing human brain tissue sampling methods are not presently optimized for collecting NSS nuclei, creating a significant roadblock for NSS research. For instance, the National Institute on Aging-Alzheimer's Association guidelines¹⁰⁵ recommend sampling the basal ganglia at the level of the anterior commissure, pons, and midbrain to collect the basal nucleus of Meynert, LC, and SN, respectively. This scheme is too coarse for capturing the precise anatomical levels, landmarks, and intranuclear gradients of vulnerability. The basal nucleus of Meynert includes several subnuclei^{106,107} with varied vulnerability to AD-type neurodegeneration throughout.¹⁰⁸ Similarly, the LC exhibits notable gradients of vulnerability, with the middle rostro-caudal third showing high susceptibility and the caudal third showing relative sparing.^{75,109,110}

Furthermore, most brain sampling schemes for age-related neuropathology do not include the hypothalamus, which contains many

NSS nuclei showing early vulnerability for AD. Despite its complicated cytoarchitectonics, the main hypothalamic structures of interest can be identified in coronal hypothalamic slides by Nissl staining and immunohistochemistry. The advent of *in situ* “-omics” and methods enabling RNA sequencing from formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded brain tissue has expanded the opportunities for molecular studies in individual NSS nuclei and subnuclei, which systematic sampling of the structures can enable.

2.5 | Response analysis

AD's behavioral and psychiatric symptoms begin in the early pathological stages.¹⁹ In many individuals with AD, these symptoms are refractory to treatments by conventional anti-depressant and anxiolytic medications.^{111,112} Moreover, these and other psychotropic medications, including sedative drugs, sleep medication, and antipsychotics, often have harmful side effects in AD.¹¹³ This observation is not surprising given the magnitude of degeneration, including frank cell loss, in specific NSS nuclei in AD. In fact, the etiology of these symptoms in AD may widely differ from that in the general population, necessitating research on appropriate disease- or individual-level management of symptoms. Nevertheless, tracking how patients respond to various psychiatric medications, including novel or repurposed agents, in a longitudinal design may facilitate earlier disease detection, subtyping, prognostic stratification, and improved understanding of functional neurobiological AD changes.

3 | MODEL SYSTEMS

A mechanistic understanding of NSS vulnerability in AD and NSS contributions to disease progression remains limited. *In vivo* research in vertebrate animal models benefits from the phylogenetic conservation of NSS nuclei. For example, the LC has been identified in all Gnathostomata lineages, placing its evolutionary origins to at least 380 million years ago.¹¹⁴ As such, even aquatic models such as zebrafish¹¹⁵ offer a platform for research on NSS selective vulnerability.

Unlike their mouse counterparts, rat AD models can develop endogenous hyperphosphorylated tau, even when not carrying a tauopathy transgene.¹¹⁶ The TgF344-AD rat, which carries a transgene expressing mutant human amyloid precursor protein and presenilin 1,¹¹⁷ shows tau pathology in the LC before the emergence of forebrain pathology,¹¹⁶ making it a good option for preclinical studies incorporating subcortical pathologic lesions in AD. Other vulnerable NSS nuclei, such as the serotonergic DRN, histaminergic tuberomammillary nucleus, orexin/hypocretin system, and cholinergic nuclei have yet to be characterized in this model. While the TgF344-AD rat has several advantages for studying NSS, mouse models (e.g., APPsw/PS1, P301S, 3xTg-AD, 5xFAD) are often used due to the available genetic toolkits to manipulate their cell signaling networks. However, while some of these transgenic strains demonstrate pathology within brainstem regions, such as A β oligomers and hyperphosphorylated tau in the LC,^{26,118-120} they do not recapitulate the temporal disease patterns observed in

humans because the ubiquitous promoters used lead to simultaneous overexpression of A β or pathological tau throughout the brain. Also, mouse tau does not contain the full human complement of isoforms and is aggregation-resistant.^{64,65} Notably, most AD cases are sporadic, and observations made in models of familial-based systems will not always be generalizable.

Although transgenic rodent models of familial tauopathy exist, their utility for examining NSS vulnerability in AD is limited. While some subcortical systems appear similarly affected in rare, autosomal dominant forms of AD,^{121,122} developing new preclinical models of sporadic AD that induce susceptibility to pathologic lesions in NSS is of utmost importance. It is also unclear whether NSS nuclei have the same vulnerability profile in humans and animal models. Emerging mouse models of sporadic AD from consortiums such as Model Organism Development & Evaluation for Late-Onset Alzheimer's Disease should be systematically examined for disease-related phenotypes in NSS nuclei and existing phenotyping schemes.

Due to the small sizes of the NSS nuclei, it remains challenging to analyze their molecular, cellular, and physiological properties in vivo. In vitro models could be particularly useful for defining the effects of AD-type lesions on NSS neurons. Induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC) and fibroblast-based 2D and organoid differentiation protocols are also being developed to specify noradrenergic, serotonergic, and cholinergic neuron fates.^{123–126} Unfortunately, the cells generated from existing protocols represent forebrain neuron populations rather than the isodendritic hindbrain neurons. This limitation is also the case for the SH-SY5Y line,^{127,128} which is often used for LC research. Given the selective vulnerability of NSS neurons to neurodegeneration, developing protocols to generate human cells that reflect hindbrain neuron populations is a high priority and would meaningfully complement animal models, biomarker findings, and neuropathology through high-throughput molecular genetic screens, drug screens, electrophysiological recording, or cell signaling assays.

An essential step toward generating valid in vitro differentiation protocols includes investment in research on the developmental origins of NSS nuclei.¹²⁹ Understanding of specific developmental origins of NSS beyond recognizing broad categories of transcription factors involved in hindbrain fate is deficient. For example, the LC has been thought to hold a single developmental origin within dorsal rhombomere-1 (r1).^{130,131} More recent genetic fate-mapping studies examining the expression of *Fgf8* and *Pax7* have disputed this perception by expanding the developmental origins of the LC to include the isthmus and regions outside of the alar plate of the dorsal neural tube.^{131–134}

4 | INTERVENTIONS

As attempts to reverse neurodegeneration are yet to be available, intervention should focus on attempting to reduce or prevent widespread neuronal loss. Targeting NSS function may mitigate neuronal loss and behavioral and psychiatric manifestations of AD. As AD pathology in NSS may be detectable in mid-life well before the

typical age by which individuals with cognitive decline seek medical attention,^{130,131} interventions during this period are likely to have a stronger impact on late-life brain health than interventions initiated during the cognitive stages of AD.^{132,133}

4.1 | Symptomatic therapies

The currently available pharmacological therapies to treat cognitive symptoms in AD-type dementia are based on cholinergic or glutaminergic neurotransmitter deficits, which play roles in distinct cognitive dysfunctions.^{135–137} Cholinesterase inhibitors are modestly effective and widely used for mitigating cognitive symptoms associated with degeneration of the basal forebrain.¹³⁸

In addition to cholinesterase inhibitors, existing results from clinical trials suggest that other NSS targeting treatments can be effective in AD. In a phase III trial, the orexin receptor antagonist suvorexant improved sleep in participants with mild to moderate AD.¹³⁹ Atomoxetine, a clinically approved NE transporter inhibitor for attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder treatment, showed improving levels of AD biomarkers in participants with mild cognitive impairment due to AD.¹⁴⁰ Other neurotransmitter-based approaches currently under investigation include guanfacine, brexpiprazole, and escitalopram.¹⁴¹ Still, symptomatic agents targeting cognitive enhancement or neuropsychiatric symptoms currently comprise less than one fifth of all ongoing AD clinical trials.

Neuropsychiatric symptoms like sleep–wake dysfunction are both early symptoms of AD and risk factors for disease progression; thus, whether through appropriate pharmacological or non-pharmacological approaches, improving some neuropsychiatric symptoms may facilitate improved brain maintenance and resistance to AD progression.^{76,83}

Not all approaches to neuropsychiatric symptoms are appropriate for AD, though. Neuropsychiatric symptoms are controlled by multiple neurologic and endocrine systems and, thus, a neuropsychiatric disorder can have multiple etiologies. What might cause a neuropsychiatric symptom in the general population may not cause that same symptom in AD. Because of this, therapeutic approaches may differ. For example, sedative medications like benzodiazepines are commonly prescribed for insomnia in the general population but have only a modest effect on mitigating sleep–wake dysfunction in AD and are associated with severe side effects.¹⁴² Whereas comorbid psychiatric conditions often cause insomnia, stress, or poor sleep hygiene in the general population, the dysregulation of the ascending arousal network is a likely etiology for insomnia in AD. The differences in the etiology of neuropsychiatric symptoms in AD versus the general population may affect therapeutic efficacy for commonplace interventions.

4.2 | Disease-modifying interventions

Based on neuropathological, biomarker, and clinical evidence of early NSS dysfunction in AD, protecting the NSS from

neurodegenerative changes may improve AD outcomes through several pathways. NSS nuclei project widely throughout the brain as central nodes of nervous-system-wide modulatory activity. Experimental studies suggest that NSS activity is neuroprotective against cortical AD pathology via neurotransmitters' cell signaling and endocrine properties. For example, β -adrenoreceptor-mediated engagement of the cAMP receptor element-binding protein pathway by NE leads to upregulation of canonical brain-derived neurotrophic factor and nerve growth factor production loops.¹⁴³ Maintaining LC-NE integrity may help stabilize such pathways, slowing cortical neurodegeneration. In animal models, LC dysfunction exacerbates A β plaque burden in the cortex,²²⁻²⁵ potentially via microglia function.¹⁴⁴ The vast projections of the NSS may additionally facilitate disease spread into the cortex, with preclinical evidence indicating the capacity of subcortical tau to seed forebrain pathology.^{20,21}

4.3 | Cerebrovascular health

Cerebrovasculature is extensively innervated by subcortical noradrenergic, dopaminergic, serotonergic, and cholinergic neurons.¹⁴⁵⁻¹⁵⁰ Several human *post mortem* and *ante mortem* biomarker studies have established associations between NSS degeneration and markers for cerebral amyloid angiopathy, blood-brain barrier breakdown, and neurovascular integrity.¹⁵¹⁻¹⁵³ In line with this, *in vivo* studies have shown that experimental lesioning of noradrenergic^{154,155} and cholinergic^{156,157} systems leads to deleterious changes in cerebrovascular structure and function.¹⁵⁶

The NSS nuclei are uniquely exposed to the brain's extensive vascular system. The LC, SN, and several hypothalamic nuclei have some of the densest capillary beds in the brain,³³⁻³⁵ raising questions about possible vascular contributions to their vulnerability. Furthermore, NSS nuclei uniquely interface structurally with the cerebrovascular system.¹⁵⁸ For instance, tanycytes, a specialized type of glia cell, are found within circumventricular organs at the third and fourth ventricles near hypothalamic and brainstem NSS nuclei, including the LC.¹⁵⁹⁻¹⁶¹ Tanycytes serve as a tri-directional interface among CSF, blood, and these nuclei for hormone and neurotropic factor detection and release. Despite their functional importance, research on tanycytes has been limited by methodological constraints since their discovery in the 1950s.¹⁶² Recent development with single cell -omics technology is well positioned to revive research on tanycytes, fill in critical gaps about NSS neurovascular unit physiology, and uncover factors influencing vulnerability of the NSS.

There are critical knowledge gaps in the reciprocal interactions between NSS integrity and cerebrovascular health and the mechanisms by which the NSS regulates vascular tone, perfusion, permeability, and neurovascular coupling; moderate or mediate risk factors for cerebrovascular disease; and contribute to the development of cerebrovascular lesions during the early course of AD.¹⁶³ Research programs addressing these underexplored areas in human clinical series will be of critical importance for understanding the impact of NSS degeneration on postsynaptic cerebrovascular cell dysregulation

and how this relates to NSS-mediated neuronal and glial dysfunction, AD neuropathology, and alterations in functional connectivity. In model systems, work incorporating new technologies to stimulate or inhibit various afferent and efferent NSS inputs, next-generation single-cell transcriptomics, and small animal neuroimaging approaches may offer exciting new possibilities to home in on the precise mechanisms underlying NSS-associated phenomena in the cerebrovascular system within and outside of the context of AD.

4.4 | Non-pharmacological interventions

The non-pharmacologic interventions under evaluation for AD span from "electroceuticals" (i.e., transcutaneous vagal nerve stimulation [tVNS]), gene and stem-cell therapy, cognitive training, mindfulness, and relaxation, to diet and exercise.¹⁶⁴⁻¹⁷¹ While many of these interventions do not target the NSS in isolation, they do modulate NSS due to the fundamental neuromodulatory tone with which they engage.

Transcutaneous vagal nerve stimulation is being explored to improve memory function.^{167,172-175} In principle, the delivery of electrical pulses to the cymba concha in the outer ear engages the innervating vagus nerve. Signals travel via synaptic endings at the nucleus tractus solitarius to several regions, including the LC. Due to the LC's widespread projections to the neocortex, allocortex, and other NSS, tVNS may enable improved noradrenergic tone in AD.¹⁷⁶ Non-invasive stimulation of the greater occipital nerve—mediated by NSS activation—has improved memory function in studies of healthy young humans and animal models.

Observational studies have shown that lifestyle-related risk factors, like alcohol consumption, smoking, diabetes, hypertension, cerebrovascular disease, stress, anxiety, depression, and sleep-wake dysfunction are statistical contributors to the emergence and severity of AD-type dementia.^{168,169,177,178} NSS integrity is tightly linked to many of these risk factors, including sleep-wake dysfunction,¹⁷⁹⁻¹⁸² stress,¹⁸³⁻¹⁸⁵ depression,^{186,187} drug abuse,^{188,189} eating disorder,¹⁹⁰ and diabetes.^{191,192} Therefore, it is reasonable to expect that positive lifestyle changes may galvanize NSS resilience to AD. To answer these questions, studies need to incorporate better tools to measure NSS function and lifestyle factors, particularly regarding socio-economic status. The impact of lifestyle adaptations at the individual level is unknown and challenging to measure. While doctors should motivate their patients to improve their lifestyles, it is also important to not instill false hopes in the effectiveness of the individual case when necessary. Thus, while a healthy lifestyle certainly decreases the risk for AD dementia on average,¹⁷⁸ the field should more deeply explore such interventions on a physiologic level, focusing on NSS, to predict individual benefits over time.

5 | CONCLUSION

Interest in the role of NSS vulnerability in AD etiology and pathogenesis is nascent. While only several of the many nuclei affected in

TABLE 1 Domain-specific recommendations from the ISTAART Neuromodulatory Subcortical Systems PIA

Research domain	Recommendations
Clinical manifestations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop and deploy more sensitive, granular neuropsychiatric instruments in longitudinally followed cohorts to better evaluate clinical manifestations of NSS degeneration, especially for earlier AD stages. • Follow representative population-based cohorts longitudinally with serial neuropsychiatric and cognitive instruments, biomarkers (including AD biomarkers), and neuropathologic endpoints to capture age-related changes and the full range of AD neuropathologic changes versus other neuropathologic entities. • Revise AD syndromic definitions to include neuropsychiatric manifestations as supportive clinical features indicative of NSS degeneration and incorporate such symptoms as endpoints in clinical trials.
Neuropathology and biomarkers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrate AD-specific and NSS-specific biomarkers and neuropathologic endpoints in population-based cohorts to enable clinicopathological study of NSS degeneration. • Revise autopsy guidelines to more systematically sample NSS structures in neuropathologic evaluation and biobanking. • Harmonize brainstem neuropathologic work with cell and molecular biologic approaches to investigate mechanisms underlying selective vulnerability. • Develop a staging scheme for NSS degeneration to understand the order by which structures are affected, including all NSS structures. • Systematically evaluate <i>ante mortem</i> biomarkers of NSS structure integrity against gold-standard <i>post mortem</i> anatomical and neuropathological observations. • Assess all biomarker-based risk stratification frameworks in clinically and demographically diverse populations. • Develop and harmonize in vivo imaging tools and EEG for evaluation of NSS structural and functional integrity.
Pathophysiology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe and select animal models carefully, considering how each incorporates effectors of degeneration and exhibits temporal involvement patterns in NSS nuclei. • Guide the development of animal, organoid, and cell models with discovery-based "omics" in human <i>post mortem</i> tissue to understand the strengths and limitations of experimental systems. • Pursue a better understanding of pathways underlying NSS development to establish iPSC differentiation protocols into NSS-type neurons.
Interventions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Granularly document psychotropic medication use in well-characterized cohorts to enable biologically informed, hypothesis-driven response analyses. • Develop guidelines for treating neuropsychiatric symptoms in AD versus the general population informed by possibly unique etiologies. • Identify the mechanisms underlying how non-pharmacological interventions mitigate neurodegenerative disease risk.

Abbreviations: AD, Alzheimer's disease; EEG, electroencephalogram; iPSC, induced pluripotent stem cells; ISTAART, International Society to Advance Alzheimer's Research and Treatment; NSS, neuromodulatory subcortical system; PIA, professional interest area.

early AD stages have been investigated, the appreciation for their roles has enabled novel perspectives on neurodegenerative motifs and clinical paradigms. Notably, the study of NSS vulnerability has required the integration of numerous disciplines from throughout the AD field (Table 1). We propose that additional investment in multidisciplinary approaches to understanding NSS selective vulnerability and consequences of NSS dysfunction and degeneration will accelerate the establishment of better diagnostic frameworks, identification of potent therapeutic targets, and understanding of core effectors of age-related brain diseases. A comprehensive understanding of NSS degeneration requires studies on central themes in cell biology, systems neuroscience, bioinformatics, physiology, neuropathology, neuropsychology, medical physics, analytical chemistry, epidemiology, and public health. The NSS PIA will continue to congregate research teams united by a focus on NSS degeneration in AD, train new investigators, and serve as a forum for developing research strategies to bridge translational gaps and deliver better outcomes for patients and families.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This manuscript was facilitated by the Alzheimer's Association International Society to Advance Alzheimer's Research and Treatment

(ISTAART), through the Neuromodulatory Subcortical System professional interest area (PIA). The views and opinions expressed by authors in this publication represent those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the PIA membership, ISTAART, or the Alzheimer's Association. The authors wish to acknowledge the following funding sources: (A.J.E.) NIH T32GM139780, UC Berkeley Greater Good Science Center; (M.A.K.) NIA F31AG069502; (D.W.) NIA R01AG062581, NIA RF1AG061175; (N.F.) Alzheimer's Association AACSF-21-723056, Global Brain Health Institute, Alzheimer's Association and Alzheimer's Society UK GBHI-ALZ-UK-21-723831; (K.Y.L.) Medical Research Council UK MR/S021418/1; (M.M.) NIH R01AG025340; (M.J.B.) Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) Project-ID 42589996 – SFB 1436 Project A08 and the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF, funding code 01ED2102B) under the aegis of JPND; (S.D.) NSF GRFP DGE1418060; (D.H.) CRC 1436, CRC 1315, ARUK SRF 2018B-004, CBBS Neural Network 17; (J.R.W.) NIA F32AG074625, NIA P30AG066515; (M.Le.) Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft Project-ID 42589994; (S.E.C.) NIH P01G014449-24, NIH P30AG072931-06, NIH R01AG060731-04; (J.M.S.) NHMRC 1193857, The University of Sydney, Viertel/Bellberry Foundation;

(A.I.L.) P30AG066511, U54AG065187, U01AG061357; (E.L.) Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft 362321501, Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft RTG2413; (M.Lu.) European Regional Development Fund ZS/2016/04/78113; (M.V.E.) BrightFocus Foundation A20211016F; (Q.W.) NIH RF1AG067729, NIH R01AG064664, NIH RF1 AG056815; (E.M.V.) U01AA025481-0551; (J.R.G.) NIA K23AG058805; (W.F.) Alzheimer Nederland WE.03-2018-13; (C.B.) European Committee HORIZON-INFRA-2021-TECH-01-01 GAP-101058516, European Committee H2021-MSCA-DN-2021; (D.H.) CRC 1436, CRC 1315, ARUK SRF 2018B-004, CBBS Neural Network 17; (W.S.K.) NIA R01AG050595, NIA R01AG076838; (H.I.L.J.) NIH R01AG062559, NIH R01AG068062, NIH R21AG074220, Alzheimer's Association AARG-22-920434, Alzheimer Nederland WE.03-2019-02; (L.T.G.) NIH K24AG053435, R01AG060477, R01 AG064314, R01AG070826, R01AG056573.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

A.J.E. has received support for travel from the Rainwater Charitable Foundation and Deutsches Zentrum für Neurodegenerative Erkrankungen, has received consulting fees from Epiodyne Inc., holds stock in Eiger Biopharmaceuticals, is a science eEditor for *Alzheimer's & Dementia: The Journal of the Alzheimer's Association*, and serves on the executive committee for the Neuromodulatory Subcortical Systems PIA of ISTAART. S.T. is an advisory board member for Roche, Eisai, Biogen, and Grifols and is an independent data monitoring board member for Biogen, is a senior associate editor for *Alzheimer's & Dementia: The Journal of the Alzheimer's Association*, and served on the executive committee for the Neuromodulatory Subcortical Systems PIA of ISTAART during the time this manuscript was written. A.I.L. has received consulting fees from Biogen, Karuna, Cognito Therapeutics, and Genuv. Q.W. is listed on US Patent applications 63/138.118 & 63/305.621, and holds stock in Terran Biosciences. C.B. has received consulting fees from Cyclerion Therapeutics, serves on the steering committee of the Italian Society of Psychophysiology, and serves as the immediate past chair of the Electrophysiology PIA of ISTAART. L.T.G. has received support from the Rainwater Charitable Foundation, support for travel from the Alzheimer's Association, and serves on the executive committee for the Neuromodulatory Subcortical Systems PIA of ISTAART. H.I.L.J., M.J.D., A.J.W., D.W., N.F., S.E.C., C.S., M.K., and G.S. served on the executive committee (unpaid) for the Neuromodulatory Subcortical Systems PIA of ISTAART during the time this manuscript was written. K.L., M.M., M.J.B., S.D., D.H., J.R.W., M.Le., J.M.S., O.E., I.R., E.L., M.Lu., C.S., M.V.E., E.M.V., F.R., L.H., S.V., W.M.F., Y.Y., M.M., C.L., M.B., A.S., J.R.G., W.S.K., and R.H. have no conflicts to disclose. Author disclosures are available in the [supporting information](#).

REFERENCES

1. Azevedo FA, Carvalho LR, Grinberg LT, et al. Equal numbers of neuronal and nonneuronal cells make the human brain an isometrically scaled-up primate brain. *J Comp Neurol*. 2009;513:532-541.
2. Bargmann CI, Marder E. From the connectome to brain function. *Nat Methods*. 2013;10:483-490.
3. Marder E. Neuromodulation of neuronal circuits: back to the future. *Neuron*. 2012;76:1-11.
4. Whitehouse PJ, Price DL, Struble RG, Clark AW, Coyle JT, Delon MR. Alzheimer's disease and senile dementia: loss of neurons in the basal forebrain. *Science*. 1982;215:1237-1239.
5. Curcio CA, Kemper T. Nucleus raphe dorsalis in dementia of the Alzheimer type: neurofibrillary changes and neuronal packing density. *J Neuropathol Exp Neurol*. 1984;43:359-368.
6. Mann DM, Lincoln J, Yates PO, Stamp JE, Toper S. Changes in the monoamine containing neurones of the human CNS in senile dementia. *Br J Psychiatry*. 1980;136:533-541.
7. Mufson EJ, Mash DC, Hersh LB. Neurofibrillary tangles in cholinergic pedunclopontine neurons in Alzheimer's disease. *Ann Neurol*. 1988;24:623-629.
8. Ohm TG, Braak H. Auditory brainstem nuclei in Alzheimer's disease. *Neurosci Lett*. 1989;96:60-63.
9. Yamamoto T, Hirano A. Nucleus raphe dorsalis in Alzheimer's disease: neurofibrillary tangles and loss of large neurons. *Ann Neurol*. 1985;17:573-577.
10. Zweig RM, Ross CA, Hedreen JC, et al. The neuropathology of aminergic nuclei in Alzheimer's disease. *Ann Neurol*. 1988;24:233-242.
11. Scinto LF, Wu CK, Firla KM, Daffner KR, Saroff D, Geula C. Focal pathology in the Edinger-Westphal nucleus explains pupillary hypersensitivity in Alzheimer's disease. *Acta Neuropathol*. 1999;97:557-564.
12. Parvizi J, Van Hoesen GW, Damasio A. The selective vulnerability of brainstem nuclei to Alzheimer's disease. *Ann Neurol*. 2001;49:53-66.
13. Birks J. Cholinesterase inhibitors for Alzheimer's disease. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2006;CD005593.
14. Braak H, Del Tredici K, Rub U, de Vos RA, Jansen Steur EN, Braak E. Staging of brain pathology related to sporadic Parkinson's disease. *Neurobiol Aging*. 2003;24:197-211.
15. Grinberg LT, Rueb U, Alho AT, Heinsen H. Brainstem pathology and non-motor symptoms in PD. *J Neurol Sci*. 2010;289:81-88.
16. Rub U, Stratmann K, Heinsen H, et al. The Brainstem Tau Cytoskeletal Pathology of Alzheimer's disease: a brief historical overview and description of its anatomical distribution pattern, evolutionary features, pathogenetic and clinical relevance. *Curr Alzheimer Res*. 2016;13:1178-1197.
17. Stratmann K, Heinsen H, Korf HW, et al. Precortical phase of Alzheimer's disease (AD)-related tau cytoskeletal pathology. *Brain Pathol*. 2016;26:371-386.
18. Jacobs HIL, Riphagen JM, Ramakers I, Verhey FRJ. Alzheimer's disease pathology: pathways between central norepinephrine activity, memory, and neuropsychiatric symptoms. *Mol Psychiatry*. 2021;26:897-906.
19. Ehrenberg AJ, Suemoto CK, Franca Resende EP, et al. Neuropathologic correlates of psychiatric symptoms in Alzheimer's disease. *J Alzheimers Dis*. 2018;66:115-126.
20. Kang SS, Liu X, Ahn EH, et al. Norepinephrine metabolite DOPEGAL activates AEP and pathological Tau aggregation in locus coeruleus. *J Clin Invest*. 2020;130:422-437.
21. Ghosh A, Torraville SE, Mukherjee B, et al. An experimental model of Braak's pretangle proposal for the origin of Alzheimer's disease: the role of locus coeruleus in early symptom development. *Alzheimers Res Ther*. 2019;11:59.
22. Heneka MT, Ramanathan M, Jacobs AH, et al. Locus ceruleus degeneration promotes Alzheimer pathogenesis in amyloid precursor protein 23 transgenic mice. *J Neurosci*. 2006;26:1343-1354.
23. Kalinin S, Gavriluk V, Polak PE, et al. Noradrenaline deficiency in brain increases beta-amyloid plaque burden in an animal model of Alzheimer's disease. *Neurobiol Aging*. 2007;28:1206-1214.
24. Jardanhazi-Kurutz D, Kummer MP, Terwel D, et al. Induced LC degeneration in APP/PS1 transgenic mice accelerates early cerebral amyloidosis and cognitive deficits. *Neurochem Int*. 2010;57:375-382.
25. Rey NL, Jardanhazi-Kurutz D, Terwel D, et al. Locus coeruleus degeneration exacerbates olfactory deficits in APP/PS1 transgenic mice. *Neurobiol Aging*. 2012;33:426e1-11.

26. Chalermpananupap T, Schroeder JP, Rorabaugh JM, et al. Locus coeruleus ablation exacerbates cognitive deficits, neuropathology, and lethality in P301S tau transgenic mice. *J Neurosci*. 2018;38:74-92.
27. Schmitz TW, Soreq H, Poirier J, Spreng RN. Longitudinal basal forebrain degeneration interacts with TREM2/C3 biomarkers of inflammation in presymptomatic Alzheimer's disease. *J Neurosci*. 2020;40:1931-1942.
28. Berridge CW, Waterhouse BD. The locus coeruleus-noradrenergic system: modulation of behavioral state and state-dependent cognitive processes. *Brain Res Brain Res Rev*. 2003;42:33-84.
29. Sara SJ. The locus coeruleus and noradrenergic modulation of cognition. *Nat Rev Neurosci*. 2009;10:211-223.
30. Arendt T. Alzheimer's disease as a loss of differentiation control in a subset of neurons that retain immature features in the adult brain. *Neurobiol Aging*. 2000;21:783-796.
31. Mattson MP, Magnus T. Ageing and neuronal vulnerability. *Nat Rev Neurosci*. 2006;7:278-294.
32. Mesulam MM. Neuroplasticity failure in Alzheimer's disease: bridging the gap between plaques and tangles. *Neuron*. 1999;24:521-529.
33. Finley KH, Cobb S. The capillary bed of the locus coeruleus. *J Comp Neurol*. 1940;73:49-58.
34. Finley KH. The capillary beds of the paraventricular and supra-optic nuclei of the hypothalamus. *J Comp Neurol*. 1939;71:1-19.
35. Finley KH. Angio-architecture of the substantia nigra and its pathogenic significance. *Arch Neurol Psychiatry*. 1936;36:118-127.
36. Braak H, Thal DR, Ghebremedhin E, Del Tredici K. Stages of the pathologic process in Alzheimer disease: age categories from 1 to 100 years. *J Neuropathol Exp Neurol*. 2011;70:960-969.
37. Duyckaerts C, Braak H, Brion JP, et al. PART is part of Alzheimer disease. *Acta Neuropathol*. 2015;129:749-756.
38. Jessen F, Amariglio RE, van Boxtel M, et al. A conceptual framework for research on subjective cognitive decline in preclinical Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2014;10:844-852.
39. Jack CR, Jr., Bennett DA, Blennow K, et al. NIA-AA research framework: toward a biological definition of Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2018;14:535-562.
40. Betts MJ, Kirilina E, Otaduy MCG, et al. Locus coeruleus imaging as a biomarker for noradrenergic dysfunction in neurodegenerative diseases. *Brain*. 2019;142:2558-2571.
41. Sulzer D, Cassidy C, Horga G, et al. Neuromelanin detection by magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and its promise as a biomarker for Parkinson's disease. *NPJ Parkinsons Dis*. 2018;4:11.
42. Lee JY, Martin-Bastida A, Murueta-Goyena A, et al. Multimodal brain and retinal imaging of dopaminergic degeneration in Parkinson disease. *Nat Rev Neurol*. 2022;18:203-220.
43. Billot B, Bocchetta M, Todd E, Dalca AV, Rohrer JD, Iglesias JE. Automated segmentation of the hypothalamus and associated subunits in brain MRI. *Neuroimage*. 2020;223:117287.
44. Greve DN, Billot B, Cordero D, et al. A deep learning toolbox for automatic segmentation of subcortical limbic structures from MRI images. *Neuroimage*. 2021;244:118610.
45. Fritz HJ, Ray N, Dyrba M, Sorg C, Teipel S, Grothe MJ. The corticotopic organization of the human basal forebrain as revealed by regionally selective functional connectivity profiles. *Hum Brain Mapp*. 2019;40:868-878.
46. Lynch CJ, Power JD, Scult MA, Dubin M, Gunning FM, Liston C. Rapid precision functional mapping of individuals using multi-echo fMRI. *Cell Rep*. 2020;33:108540.
47. Puckett AM, Bollmann S, Poser BA, Palmer J, Barth M, Cunnington R. Using multi-echo simultaneous multi-slice (SMS) EPI to improve functional MRI of the subcortical nuclei of the basal ganglia at ultra-high field (7T). *Neuroimage*. 2018;172:886-895.
48. Risk BB, Murden RJ, Wu J, et al. Which multiband factor should you choose for your resting-state fMRI study? *Neuroimage*. 2021;234:117965.
49. Miletic S, Bazin PL, Weiskopf N, van der Zwaag W, Forstmann BU, Trampel R. fMRI protocol optimization for simultaneously studying small subcortical and cortical areas at 7 T. *Neuroimage*. 2020;219:116992.
50. Munn BR, Muller EJ, Wainstein G, Shine JM. The ascending arousal system shapes neural dynamics to mediate awareness of cognitive states. *Nat Commun*. 2021;12:6016.
51. Doppler CEJ, Kinnerup MB, Brune C, et al. Regional locus coeruleus degeneration is uncoupled from noradrenergic terminal loss in Parkinson's disease. *Brain*. 2021;144:2732-2744.
52. Tiepolt S, Meyer PM, Patt M, et al. PET imaging of cholinergic neurotransmission in neurodegenerative disorders. *J Nucl Med*. 2022;63:335-445.
53. Weinschenker D. Long road to ruin: noradrenergic dysfunction in neurodegenerative disease. *Trends Neurosci*. 2018;41:211-223.
54. Mather M, Joo Yoo H, Clewett DV, et al. Higher locus coeruleus MRI contrast is associated with lower parasympathetic influence over heart rate variability. *Neuroimage*. 2017;150:329-335.
55. Jacobs HI, Priovoulos N, Poser BA, et al. Dynamic behavior of the locus coeruleus during arousal-related memory processing in a multi-modal 7T fMRI paradigm. *Elife*. 2020;9:e52059.
56. Strauch C, Wang CA, Einhauser W, Van der Stigchel S, Naber M. Pupilometry as an integrated readout of distinct attentional networks. *Trends Neurosci*. 2022;45:635-647.
57. Murphy PR, O'Connell RG, O'Sullivan M, Robertson IH, Balsters JH. Pupil diameter covaries with BOLD activity in human locus coeruleus. *Hum Brain Mapp*. 2014;35:4140-4154.
58. Sterpenich V, D'Argembeau A, Desseilles M, et al. The locus coeruleus is involved in the successful retrieval of emotional memories in humans. *J Neurosci*. 2006;26:7416-7423.
59. Grueschow M, Stenz N, Thorn H, et al. Real-world stress resilience is associated with the responsiveness of the locus coeruleus. *Nat Commun*. 2021;12:2275.
60. Clewett DV, Huang R, Velasco R, Lee TH, Mather M. Locus coeruleus activity strengthens prioritized memories under arousal. *J Neurosci*. 2018;38:1558-1574.
61. Alnaes D, Sneve MH, Espeseth T, Endestad T, van de Pavert SH, Laeng B. Pupil size signals mental effort deployed during multiple object tracking and predicts brain activity in the dorsal attention network and the locus coeruleus. *J Vis*. 2014;14:1.
62. Reimer J, McGinley MJ, Liu Y, et al. Pupil fluctuations track rapid changes in adrenergic and cholinergic activity in cortex. *Nat Commun*. 2016;7:13289.
63. Cazettes F, Reato D, Morais JP, Renart A, Mainen ZF. Phasic activation of dorsal raphe serotonergic neurons increases pupil size. *Curr Biol*. 2021;31:192-197.e4.
64. Joshi S, Gold JI. Pupil size as a window on neural substrates of cognition. *Trends Cogn Sci*. 2020;24:466-480.
65. Babiloni C, Arakaki X, Azami H, et al. Measures of resting state EEG rhythms for clinical trials in Alzheimer's disease: recommendations of an expert panel. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2021;17:1528-1553.
66. Babiloni C, Blinowska K, Bonanni L, et al. What electrophysiology tells us about Alzheimer's disease: a window into the synchronization and connectivity of brain neurons. *Neurobiol Aging*. 2020;85:58-73.
67. Leung DKY, Chan WC, Spector A, Wong GHY. Prevalence of depression, anxiety, and apathy symptoms across dementia stages: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int J Geriatr Psychiatry*. 2021;36:1330-1344.
68. Charney DS, Redmond DE, Jr. Neurobiological mechanisms in human anxiety. Evidence supporting central noradrenergic hyperactivity. *Neuropharmacology*. 1983;22:1531-1536.
69. Charney DS, Grillon C, Bremner JD. The neurobiological basis of anxiety and fear: circuits, mechanisms, and neurochemical interactions (part I). *Neuroscientist*. 1998;4:35-44.

70. Rosenberg PB, Nowrangi MA, Lyketsos CG. Neuropsychiatric symptoms in Alzheimer's disease: what might be associated brain circuits? *Mol Aspects Med.* 2015;43-44:25-37.
71. Liu KY, Stringer AE, Reeves SJ, Howard RJ. The neurochemistry of agitation in Alzheimer's disease: a systematic review. *Ageing Res Rev.* 2018;43:99-107.
72. Liguori C, Placidi F, Izzi F, Spanetta M, Mercuri NB, Di Pucchio A. Sleep dysregulation, memory impairment, and CSF biomarkers during different levels of neurocognitive functioning in Alzheimer's disease course. *Alzheimers Res Ther.* 2020;12:5.
73. Liguori C, Romigi A, Nuccetelli M, et al. Orexinergic system dysregulation, sleep impairment, and cognitive decline in Alzheimer disease. *JAMA Neurol.* 2014;71:1498-1505.
74. Scammell TE, Arrigoni E, Lipton JO. Neural circuitry of wakefulness and sleep. *Neuron.* 2017;93:747-765.
75. Theofilas P, Ehrenberg AJ, Dunlop S, et al. Locus coeruleus volume and cell population changes during Alzheimer's disease progression: a stereological study in human postmortem brains with potential implication for early-stage biomarker discovery. *Alzheimers Dement.* 2017;13:236-246.
76. Van Egroo M, Narbutas J, Chylinski D, et al. Sleep-wake regulation and the hallmarks of the pathogenesis of Alzheimer's disease. *Sleep.* 2019;42:zsz017.
77. Lew CH, Petersen C, Neylan TC, Grinberg LT. Tau-driven degeneration of sleep- and wake-regulating neurons in Alzheimer's disease. *Sleep Med Rev.* 2021;60:101541.
78. Van Egroo M, van Hooren RWE, Jacobs HIL. Associations between locus coeruleus integrity and nocturnal awakenings in the context of Alzheimer's disease plasma biomarkers: a 7T MRI study. *Alzheimers Res Ther.* 2021;13:159.
79. Van Egroo M, Koshmanova E, Vandewalle G, Jacobs HIL. Importance of the locus coeruleus-norepinephrine system in sleep-wake regulation: implications for aging and Alzheimer's disease. *Sleep Med Rev.* 2022;62:101592.
80. Kjaerby C, Andersen M, Hauglund N, et al. Memory-enhancing properties of sleep depend on the oscillatory amplitude of norepinephrine. *Nat Neurosci.* 2022;25:1059-1070.
81. Cassidy CM, Therriault J, Pascoal TA, et al. Association of locus coeruleus integrity with Braak stage and neuropsychiatric symptom severity in Alzheimer's disease. *Neuropsychopharmacology.* 2022;47:1128-1136.
82. Oh J, Eser RA, Ehrenberg AJ, et al. Profound degeneration of wake-promoting neurons in Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimers Dement.* 2019;15:1253-1263.
83. Wang C, Holtzman DM. Bidirectional relationship between sleep and Alzheimer's disease: role of amyloid, tau, and other factors. *Neuropsychopharmacology.* 2020;45:104-120.
84. Cools R, Arnsten AFT. Neuromodulation of prefrontal cortex cognitive function in primates: the powerful roles of monoamines and acetylcholine. *Neuropsychopharmacology.* 2022;47:309-328.
85. Thiele A, Bellgrove MA. Neuromodulation of Attention. *Neuron.* 2018;97:769-785.
86. Mather M, Clewett D, Sakaki M, Harley CW. Norepinephrine ignites local hotspots of neuronal excitation: how arousal amplifies selectivity in perception and memory. *Behav Brain Sci.* 2016;39:e200.
87. Dahl MJ, Mather M, Werkle-Bergner M. Noradrenergic modulation of rhythmic neural activity shapes selective attention. *Trends Cogn Sci.* 2022;26:38-52.
88. Li SC, Lindenberger U, Sikstrom S. Aging cognition: from neuromodulation to representation. *Trends Cogn Sci.* 2001;5:479-486.
89. Mather M, Harley CW. The locus coeruleus: essential for maintaining cognitive function and the aging brain. *Trends Cogn Sci.* 2016;20:214-226.
90. Braver TS, Barch DM. A theory of cognitive control, aging cognition, and neuromodulation. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev.* 2002;26:809-817.
91. Backman L, Lindenberger U, Li SC, Nyberg L. Linking cognitive aging to alterations in dopamine neurotransmitter functioning: recent data and future avenues. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev.* 2010;34:670-677.
92. Backman L, Nyberg L, Lindenberger U, Li SC, Farde L. The correlative triad among aging, dopamine, and cognition: current status and future prospects. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev.* 2006;30:791-807.
93. Nyberg L, Karalija N, Salami A, et al. Dopamine D2 receptor availability is linked to hippocampal-caudate functional connectivity and episodic memory. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2016;113:7918-7923.
94. Elman JA, Puckett OK, Beck A, et al. MRI-assessed locus coeruleus integrity is heritable and associated with multiple cognitive domains, mild cognitive impairment, and daytime dysfunction. *Alzheimers Dement.* 2021;17:1017-1025.
95. Liu KY, Kievit RA, Tsvetanov KA, et al. Noradrenergic-dependent functions are associated with age-related locus coeruleus signal intensity differences. *Nat Commun.* 2020;11:1712.
96. Dahl MJ, Mather M, Duzel S, et al. Rostral locus coeruleus integrity is associated with better memory performance in older adults. *Nat Hum Behav.* 2019;3:1203-1214.
97. Cummings JL, Mega M, Gray K, Rosenberg-Thompson S, Carusi DA, Gornbein J. The Neuropsychiatric Inventory: comprehensive assessment of psychopathology in dementia. *Neurology.* 1994;44:2308-2314.
98. Berron D, Ziegler G, Vieweg P, et al. Feasibility of digital memory assessments in an unsupervised and remote study setting. *Front Digit Health.* 2022;4:892997.
99. Ludtke S, Hermann W, Kirste T, Benes H, Teipel S. An algorithm for actigraphy-based sleep/wake scoring: comparison with polysomnography. *Clin Neurophysiol.* 2021;132:137-145.
100. Attems J, Thomas A, Jellinger K. Correlations between cortical and subcortical tau pathology. *Neuropathol Appl Neurobiol.* 2012;38:582-590.
101. Arendt T, Bruckner MK, Morawski M, Jager C, Gertz HJ. Early neurone loss in Alzheimer's disease: cortical or subcortical? *Acta Neuropathol Commun.* 2015;3:10.
102. Ehrenberg AJ, Nguy AK, Theofilas P, et al. Quantifying the accretion of hyperphosphorylated tau in the locus coeruleus and dorsal raphe nucleus: the pathological building blocks of early Alzheimer's disease. *Neuropathol Appl Neurobiol.* 2017;43:393-408.
103. Lyness SA, Zarow C, Chui HC. Neuron loss in key cholinergic and aminergic nuclei in Alzheimer disease: a meta-analysis. *Neurobiol Aging.* 2003;24:1-23.
104. Andres-Benito P, Fernandez-Duenas V, Carmona M, et al. Locus coeruleus at asymptomatic early and middle Braak stages of neurofibrillary tangle pathology. *Neuropathol Appl Neurobiol.* 2017;43:373-392.
105. Montine TJ, Phelps CH, Beach TG, et al. National Institute on Aging-Alzheimer's Association guidelines for the neuropathologic assessment of Alzheimer's disease: a practical approach. *Acta Neuropathol.* 2012;123:1-11.
106. Grinberg LT, Heinsen H. Computer-assisted 3D reconstruction of the human basal forebrain complex. *Dement Neuropsychol.* 2007;1:140-146.
107. Mesulam MM, Geula C. Nucleus basalis (Ch4) and cortical cholinergic innervation in the human brain: observations based on the distribution of acetylcholinesterase and choline acetyltransferase. *JCompNeurol.* 1988;275:216-240.
108. Liu AK, Chang RC, Pearce RK, Gentleman SM. Nucleus basalis of Meynert revisited: anatomy, history and differential involvement in Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease. *Acta Neuropathol.* 2015;129:527-540.
109. Ehrenberg AJ, Nguy AK, Theofilas P, et al. Quantifying the accretion of hyperphosphorylated tau in the locus coeruleus and dorsal raphe nucleus: the pathological building blocks of early Alzheimer's disease. *Neuropathol Appl Neurobiol.* 2017;43:393-408.

110. Betts MJ, Cardenas-Blanco A, Kanowski M, et al. Locus coeruleus MRI contrast is reduced in Alzheimer's disease dementia and correlates with CSF Aβ levels. *Alzheimers Dement (Amst)*. 2019;11:281-285.
111. Banerjee S, Hellier J, Dewey M, et al. Sertraline or mirtazapine for depression in dementia (HTA-SADD): a randomised, multicentre, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2011;378:403-411.
112. Jones HE, Joshi A, Shenkin S, Mead GE. The effect of treatment with selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors in comparison to placebo in the progression of dementia: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Age Ageing*. 2016;45:448-456.
113. Wucherer D, Thyrian JR, Eichler T, et al. Drug-related problems in community-dwelling primary care patients screened positive for dementia. *Int Psychogeriatr*. 2017;29:1857-1868.
114. Wang S, Wang Z, Mu Y. Locus coeruleus in non-mammalian vertebrates. *Brain Sci*. 2022;12.
115. Ma PM. Catecholaminergic systems in the zebrafish. II. Projection pathways and pattern of termination of the locus coeruleus. *J Comp Neurol*. 1994;344:256-269.
116. Rorabaugh JM, Chalermpananupap T, Botz-Zapp CA, et al. Chemo-genetic locus coeruleus activation restores reversal learning in a rat model of Alzheimer's disease. *Brain*. 2017;140:3023-3038.
117. Cohen RM, Rezaei-Zadeh K, Weitz TM, et al. A transgenic Alzheimer rat with plaques, tau pathology, behavioral impairment, oligomeric Aβ, and frank neuronal loss. *J Neurosci*. 2013;33:6245-6256.
118. Kelly L, Seifi M, Ma R, et al. Identification of intraneuronal amyloid beta oligomers in locus coeruleus neurons of Alzheimer's patients and their potential impact on inhibitory neurotransmitter receptors and neuronal excitability. *Neuropathol Appl Neurobiol*. 2021;47:488-505.
119. Yoshiyama Y, Higuchi M, Zhang B, et al. Synapse loss and microglial activation precede tangles in a P301S tauopathy mouse model. *Neuron*. 2007;53:337-351.
120. Jankowsky JL, Zheng H. Practical considerations for choosing a mouse model of Alzheimer's disease. *Mol Neurodegener*. 2017;12:89.
121. Jacobs HIL, Becker JA, Kwong K, et al. Waning locus coeruleus integrity precedes cortical tau accrual in preclinical autosomal dominant Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2022.
122. Dahl MJ, Mather M, Werkle-Bergner M, et al. Locus coeruleus integrity is related to tau burden and memory loss in autosomal-dominant Alzheimer's disease. *Neurobiol Aging*. 2022;112:39-54.
123. Li S, Shi Y, Yao X, et al. Conversion of astrocytes and fibroblasts into functional noradrenergic neurons. *Cell Rep*. 2019;28:682-697.e7.
124. Vadodaria KC, Marchetto MC, Mertens J, Gage FH. Generating human serotonergic neurons in vitro: methodological advances. *Bioessays*. 2016;38:1123-1129.
125. Kang YH, Shivakumar SB, Son YB, et al. Comparative analysis of three different protocols for cholinergic neuron differentiation in vitro using mesenchymal stem cells from human dental pulp. *Anim Cells Syst (Seoul)*. 2019;23:275-287.
126. Pirhajati Mahabadi V, Movahedin M, Semnani S, Mirnajafi-Zadeh J, Faizi M. In vitro differentiation of neural stem cells into noradrenergic-like cells. *Int J Mol Cell Med*. 2015;4:22-31.
127. Rohm B, Holik AK, Somoza MM, et al. Nonivamide, a capsaicin analog, increases dopamine and serotonin release in SH-SY5Y cells via a TRPV1-independent pathway. *Mol Nutr Food Res*. 2013;57:2008-2018.
128. Kovalevich J, Langford D. Considerations for the use of SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cells in neurobiology. *Methods Mol Biol*. 2013;1078:9-21.
129. Okaty BW, Commons KG, Dymecki SM. Embracing diversity in the 5-HT neuronal system. *Nat Rev Neurosci*. 2019;20:397-424.
130. Schwarz LA, Luo L. Organization of the locus coeruleus-norepinephrine system. *Curr Biol*. 2015;25:R1051-R1056.
131. Aroca P, Lorente-Canovas B, Mateos FR, Puelles L. Locus coeruleus neurons originate in alar rhombomere 1 and migrate into the basal plate: studies in chick and mouse embryos. *J Comp Neurol*. 2006;496:802-818.
132. Plummer NW, Scappini EL, Smith KG, Tucker CJ, Jensen P. Two sub-populations of noradrenergic neurons in the locus coeruleus complex distinguished by expression of the dorsal neural tube marker pax7. *Front Neuroanat*. 2017;11:60.
133. Chambers D, Wilson LJ, Alfonsi F, et al. Rhombomere-specific analysis reveals the repertoire of genetic cues expressed across the developing hindbrain. *Neural Dev*. 2009;4:6.
134. Watson C, Shimogori T, Puelles L. Mouse Fgf8-Cre-LacZ lineage analysis defines the territory of the postnatal mammalian isthmus. *J Comp Neurol*. 2017;525:2782-2799.
135. Chamberlain SR, Robbins TW. Noradrenergic modulation of cognition: therapeutic implications. *J Psychopharmacol*. 2013;27:694-718.
136. Everitt BJ, Robbins TW. Central cholinergic systems and cognition. *Annu Rev Psychol*. 1997;48:649-684.
137. Robbins TW, Everitt BJ. Comparative functions of the central noradrenergic, dopaminergic and cholinergic systems. *Neuropharmacology*. 1987;26:893-901.
138. Whitehouse PJ, Price DL, Clark AW, Coyle JT, DeLong MR. Alzheimer disease: evidence for selective loss of cholinergic neurons in the nucleus basalis. *Ann Neurol*. 1981;10:122-126.
139. Herring WJ, Ceesay P, Snyder E, et al. Polysomnographic assessment of suvorexant in patients with probable Alzheimer's disease dementia and insomnia: a randomized trial. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2020;16:541-551.
140. Levey AI, Qiu D, Zhao L, et al. A phase II study repurposing atomoxetine for neuroprotection in mild cognitive impairment. *Brain*. 2022;145:1924-1938.
141. Cummings J, Lee G, Nahed P, et al. Alzheimer's disease drug development pipeline: 2022. *Alzheimers Dement (N Y)*. 2022;8:e12295.
142. Defranceco M, Marksteiner J, Fleischhacker WW, Blasko I. Use of benzodiazepines in Alzheimer's disease: a systematic review of literature. *Int J Neuropsychopharmacol*. 2015;18:pyv055.
143. Counts SE, Mufson EJ. Noradrenaline activation of neurotrophic pathways protects against neuronal amyloid toxicity. *J Neurochem*. 2010;113:649-660.
144. Heneka MT, Nadrigny F, Regen T, et al. Locus ceruleus controls Alzheimer's disease pathology by modulating microglial functions through norepinephrine. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2010;107:6058-6063.
145. Hartman BK, Zide D, Udenfriend S. The use of dopamine -hydroxylase as a marker for the central noradrenergic nervous system in rat brain. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 1972;69:2722-2726.
146. Cohen Z, Molinatti G, Hamel E. Astroglial and vascular interactions of noradrenaline terminals in the rat cerebral cortex. *J Cereb Blood Flow Metab*. 1997;17:894-904.
147. Estrada C, Hamel E, Krause DN. Biochemical evidence for cholinergic innervation of intracerebral blood vessels. *Brain Res*. 1983;266:261-270.
148. Krimer LS, Muly EC, 3rd, Williams GV, Goldman-Rakic PS. Dopaminergic regulation of cerebral cortical microcirculation. *Nat Neurosci*. 1998;1:286-289.
149. Bekar LK, Wei HS, Nedergaard M. The locus coeruleus-norepinephrine network optimizes coupling of cerebral blood volume with oxygen demand. *J Cereb Blood Flow Metab*. 2012;32:2135-2145.
150. Bonvento G, MacKenzie ET, Edvinsson L. Serotonergic innervation of the cerebral vasculature: relevance to migraine and ischaemia. *Brain Res Brain Res Rev*. 1991;16:257-263.
151. Priovoulos N, Jacobs HIL, Ivanov D, Uludag K, Verhey FRJ, Poser BA. High-resolution in vivo imaging of human locus coeruleus by magnetization transfer MRI at 3T and 7T. *Neuroimage*. 2018;168:427-436.
152. Jacobs HIL, Becker JA, Kwong K, et al. In vivo and neuropathology data support locus coeruleus integrity as indicator of

- Alzheimer's disease pathology and cognitive decline. *Sci Transl Med.* 2021;13:eabj2511.
153. Giorgi FS, Galgani A, Puglisi-Allegra S, Limanaqi F, Busceti CL, Fornai F. Locus Coeruleus and neurovascular unit: from its role in physiology to its potential role in Alzheimer's disease pathogenesis. *J Neurosci Res.* 2020;98:2406-2434.
 154. Kelly SC, McKay EC, Beck JS, Collier TJ, Dorrance AM, Counts SE. Locus coeruleus degeneration induces forebrain vascular pathology in a transgenic rat model of Alzheimer's disease. *J Alzheimers Dis.* 2019;70:371-388.
 155. Harik SI. Blood-brain barrier sodium/potassium pump: modulation by central noradrenergic innervation. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 1986;83:4067-4070.
 156. Nizari S, Wells JA, Carare RO, Romero IA, Hawkes CA. Loss of cholinergic innervation differentially affects eNOS-mediated blood flow, drainage of Abeta and cerebral amyloid angiopathy in the cortex and hippocampus of adult mice. *Acta Neuropathol Commun.* 2021;9:12.
 157. Beach TG, Potter PE, Kuo YM, et al. Cholinergic deafferentation of the rabbit cortex: a new animal model of Abeta deposition. *Neurosci Lett.* 2000;283:9-12.
 158. Felten DL, Crutcher KA. Neuronal-vascular relationships in the raphe nuclei, locus coeruleus, and substantia nigra in primates. *Am J Anat.* 1979;155:467-481.
 159. Horstmann E. Die Faserglia des Selachiergehirns. *Zeitschrift für Zellforschung und Mikroskopische Anatomie.* 1954;39:588-617.
 160. Wingstrand KG. The structure and development of the avian pituitary from a comparative and functional viewpoint [Akademisk avhandling]. Lund: Lund; 1951.
 161. Feng CY, Wiggins LM, von Bartheld CS. The locus ceruleus responds to signaling molecules obtained from the CSF by transfer through tanycytes. *J Neurosci.* 2011;31:9147-9158.
 162. Rodriguez E, Guerra M, Peruzzo B, Blazquez JL. Tanycytes: a rich morphological history to underpin future molecular and physiological investigations. *J Neuroendocrinol.* 2019;31:e12690.
 163. Iturria-Medina Y, Sotero RC, Toussaint PJ, Mateos-Perez JM, Evans AC, Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging I. Early role of vascular dysregulation on late-onset Alzheimer's disease based on multifactorial data-driven analysis. *Nat Commun.* 2016;7:11934.
 164. Chen YS, Shu K, Kang HC. Deep brain stimulation in alzheimer's disease: targeting the nucleus basalis of Meynert. *J Alzheimers Dis.* 2021;80:53-70.
 165. Chen Y, Zhang J, Zhang T, et al. Meditation treatment of Alzheimer disease and mild cognitive impairment: a protocol for systematic review. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 2020;99:e19313.
 166. Davis JJ, Fournakis N, Ellison J. Ketogenic diet for the treatment and prevention of dementia: a review. *J Geriatr Psychiatry Neurol.* 2021;34:3-10.
 167. Jacobs HI, Riphagen JM, Razat CM, Wiese S, Sack AT. Transcutaneous vagus nerve stimulation boosts associative memory in older individuals. *Neurobiol Aging.* 2015;36:1860-1867.
 168. Kivipelto M, Mangialasche F, Ngandu T. Lifestyle interventions to prevent cognitive impairment, dementia and Alzheimer disease. *Nat Rev Neurol.* 2018;14:653-666.
 169. Ko Y, Chye SM. Lifestyle intervention to prevent Alzheimer's disease. *Rev Neurosci.* 2020.
 170. Toljan K, Homolak J. Circadian changes in Alzheimer's disease: neurobiology, clinical problems, and therapeutic opportunities. *Handb Clin Neurol.* 2021;179:285-300.
 171. Bachman SL, Cole S, Yoo HJ, et al. Daily heart rate variability biofeedback training decreases locus coeruleus MRI contrast in younger adults. *medRxiv.* 2022:2022.02.04.22270468.
 172. Keute M, Wienke C, Ruhnau P, Zaehle T. Effects of transcutaneous vagus nerve stimulation (tVNS) on beta and gamma brain oscillations. *Cortex.* 2021;140:222-231.
 173. Luckey AM, McLeod SL, Robertson IH, To WT, Vanneste S. Greater occipital nerve stimulation boosts associative memory in older individuals: a randomized trial. *Neurorehabil Neural Repair.* 2020;34:1020-1029.
 174. Mertens A, Naert L, Miatton M, et al. Transcutaneous vagus nerve stimulation does not affect verbal memory performance in healthy volunteers. *Front Psychol.* 2020;11:551.
 175. Ricci L, Croce P, Lanzone J, et al. Transcutaneous vagus nerve stimulation modulates EEG microstates and delta activity in healthy subjects. *Brain Sci.* 2020;10:668.
 176. Ludwig M, Wienke C, Betts MJ, Zaehle T, Hammerer D. Current challenges in reliably targeting the noradrenergic locus coeruleus using transcutaneous auricular vagus nerve stimulation (taVNS). *Auton Neurosci.* 2021;236:102900.
 177. Rosenberg A, Mangialasche F, Ngandu T, Solomon A, Kivipelto M. Multidomain interventions to prevent cognitive impairment, Alzheimer's disease, and dementia: from FINGER to world-wide FINGERS. *J Prev Alzheimers Dis.* 2020;7:29-36.
 178. Livingston G, Huntley J, Sommerlad A, et al. Dementia prevention, intervention, and care: 2020 report of the Lancet Commission. *Lancet.* 2020;396:413-446.
 179. Lee DA, Oikonomou G, Cammidge T, et al. Neuropeptide VF neurons promote sleep via the serotonergic raphe. *Elife.* 2020;9:e54491.
 180. Mir FA, Jha SK. Locus coeruleus acid-sensing ion channels modulate sleep-wakefulness and state transition from NREM to REM sleep in the rat. *Neurosci Bull.* 2021;37:684-700.
 181. Monti JM, Lagos P, Jantos H, Torterolo P. Increased REM sleep after intra-locus coeruleus nucleus microinjection of melanin-concentrating hormone (MCH) in the rat. *Prog Neuropsychopharmacol Biol Psychiatry.* 2015;56:185-188.
 182. Swift KM, Gross BA, Frazer MA, et al. Abnormal locus coeruleus sleep activity alters sleep signatures of memory consolidation and impairs place cell stability and spatial memory. *Curr Biol.* 2018;28:3599-609e4.
 183. Eck SR, Xu SJ, Telenson A, et al. Stress regulation of sustained attention and the cholinergic attention system. *Biol Psychiatry.* 2020;88:566-575.
 184. George SA, Knox D, Curtis AL, Aldridge JW, Valentino RJ, Liberzon I. Altered locus coeruleus-norepinephrine function following single prolonged stress. *Eur J Neurosci.* 2013;37:901-909.
 185. Krystal JH, Abdallah CG, Pietrzak RH, et al. Locus coeruleus hyperactivity in posttraumatic stress disorder: answers and questions. *Biol Psychiatry.* 2018;83:197-199.
 186. Bernard R, Kerman IA, Thompson RC, et al. Altered expression of glutamate signaling, growth factor, and glia genes in the locus coeruleus of patients with major depression. *Mol Psychiatry.* 2011;16:634-646.
 187. Klimek V, Stockmeier C, Overholser J, et al. Reduced levels of norepinephrine transporters in the locus coeruleus in major depression. *J Neurosci.* 1997;17:8451-8458.
 188. Espana RA, Schmeichel BE, Berridge CW. Norepinephrine at the nexus of arousal, motivation and relapse. *Brain Res.* 2016;1641:207-216.
 189. Pomrenze MB, Walker LC, Giardino WJ. Gray areas: neuropeptide circuits linking the Edinger-Westphal and Dorsal Raphe nuclei in addiction. *Neuropharmacology.* 2021;198:108769.
 190. Ravichandran S, Bhatt RR, Pandit B, et al. Alterations in reward network functional connectivity are associated with increased food addiction in obese individuals. *Sci Rep.* 2021;11:3386.
 191. Alba-Delgado C, Cebada-Aleu A, Mico JA, Berrocoso E. Comorbid anxiety-like behavior and locus coeruleus impairment in diabetic peripheral neuropathy: a comparative study with the chronic constriction injury model. *Prog Neuropsychopharmacol Biol Psychiatry.* 2016;71:45-56.

192. Figlewicz DP, Brot MD, McCall AL, Szot P. Diabetes causes differential changes in CNS noradrenergic and dopaminergic neurons in the rat: a molecular study. *Brain Res.* 1996;736:54-60.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

How to cite this article: Ehrenberg AJ, Kelberman MA, Liu KY, et al. Priorities for research on neuromodulatory subcortical systems in Alzheimer's disease: Position paper from the NSS PIA of ISTAART. *Alzheimer's Dement.* 2023;19:2182-2196. <https://doi.org/10.1002/alz.12937>